

e-IRG mandate under Horizon Europe

Vision: *An inclusive and holistic e-Infrastructure ecosystem promoting the digital transformation in the new European Research Area*

e-IRG is an independent policy advisory body pursuing the vision of an inclusive and holistic e-Infrastructure ecosystem promoting digital transformation in the new European Research Area, spanning all areas of e-Infrastructures, namely research networking, high-throughput and high-performance computing and data infrastructures.

Mission: *The mission of e-IRG is to support policy making towards inclusive, federated, user-driven and resilient e-Infrastructures and connected services, within and between member states and associated countries, and between thematic (vertical) and generic (horizontal) e-Infrastructures.*

Rationale: Why e-IRG, current Gaps and Objectives

Despite the considerable progress achieved in EOSC, the EOSC Governance has not adequately addressed consolidation issues between horizontal European e-Infrastructure providers, nor the requirements of the thematic Research Infrastructures that are treated with lower priority and are key for EOSC Sustainability. Furthermore, EOSC seems to be focussing on establishing a 'web of fair data' whilst a diverse set of data processing and analysis capabilities are key in obtaining fundamental objectives of the EOSC as infrastructure facilitating the European Open Science policy. An unjustified separation of EOSC and e-Infrastructures stands in the way of an integral view on added value for the Research and Innovation area. The consequence of that is also evident in the current draft Horizon Europe (HE) Research Infrastructure Work Program. Directions on the connections with EuroHPC are also missing. The coordination among National Open Science Clouds (NOSCs), National Research and Education Networks (NRENs), National HTC/Grid Infrastructures (NGIs) and all other national actors through which national-pan-European links exist, is also not well considered.

e-IRG will aim to bridge the above gaps, reflecting on the above issues and providing concrete advice and recommendations to all related stakeholders. This covers EOSC related stakeholders, both horizontal (EGI, EUDAT, OpenAIRE, etc.) and thematic infrastructures (RI clusters/projects), along with GEANT/NRENs part of "Horizon Europe" and EuroHPC part of 'Digital Europe'. e-IRG, as an independent body of representatives from Member State and Associated Countries, will liaise with the EOSC Steering Board, supporting its efforts for the envisaged e-Infrastructure environment through expertise and high-level advice. e-IRG will liaise with ESFRI aiming to jointly work on further highlighting the crucial role of thematic infrastructures in EOSC for its uptake and sustainability.

With closer cooperation with the EC, e-IRG will aim to act as a clearing house getting inputs from stakeholders in these areas and providing concrete outputs and recommendations to the EC and

Member States/Associated Countries. Special attention will be given to the **national infrastructure components**, inline with the 2018 **Competitiveness Council Conclusions on EOSC** referring to e-IRG's role.

e-IRG, thus, sees its mandate as an independent body, composed of representatives from the Member States and Associated Countries, to monitor the processes and developments towards a full implementation of the e-Infrastructure Commons through the **partnerships** of all stakeholders, the **interconnectability and convergence of services** of the National Nodes (NOSCs) in the Member States and Associated Countries and at the European level. Finally, e-IRG aims to promote the digital transformation and the crucial role of e-Infrastructures in the new ERA and beyond, given also the foreseen pillars on Open Science, Open Innovation and Grand Challenges including health, digital and industry, climate, etc. The unique positioning of future e-IRG lies in providing policy advice on the intersection of EOSC ('HE'), EuroHPC ('Digital Europe') and the digital transformation of the Research and Innovation domain ('ERA') in general.

e-IRG results/outputs

A series of **policy documents** in the form of White Papers with recommendations will be developed, along with a **next e-IRG Roadmap**, fueled by the e-IRG workshops and related EOSC, EuroHPC and ESFRI events. The areas to be covered will include the topics presented below, while the Roadmap will cut across all topics. e-IRG has already been discussing these topics in its last delegates meetings, workshops and brainstorming events (e-IRG Cafés).

1. Realisation and enhancement of **partnerships among e-Infrastructures** and the **coordination and linking** ("interconnectability") between EOSC ('HE') and EDI (networking/HPC), in particular EuroHPC, towards their "convergence", both in the short and long terms.
 - a. Roadmap and recommendations on easy and transparent access to federated infrastructures; national e-Infrastructures providers' integration paradigms, pros & cons;
2. **Digital transformation** of the Research and Innovation domain reinforced by e-Infrastructures in support of the future European Research Area
3. **Federation of thematic and horizontal** e-Infrastructures, at both national and EU levels (in collaboration with ESFRI) - Good practices/models in different countries/disciplines
 - a. Analysis of the national situations: the role of NOSCs and coordination with NRENs/NGIs; Follow-up from e-IRG NN document– Collaboration with EOSC SB
 - b. Good practices of coordination and collaboration within and across e-Infrastructures and thematic research infrastructures
4. **The role of e-Infrastructures in emergency situations** such as pandemics (e.g. COVID-19) or natural disasters
 - a. Resilience and value of e-Infrastructures in transient situations, eg. COVID-19 pandemic: e-Learning, remote/virtual and transnational access to e-Infrastructures,
5. **The interchange of state-of-the-art technologies** with e-Infrastructures including Artificial Intelligence, Internet of Things, Quantum Computing, 5G.